

Table 5: Effect of the eating window in a day on Glycemia in healthy individuals and subjects at high risk for developing or with type 2 diabetes

Study	Health status Age (years) BMI (kg/m ²)	Duration and design of dietary intervention	Sample size	Description of groups	Dietary intervention	Selected clinical outcomes
Effect of Time of Feeding on Glycemia						
• Feeding/Fasting						
Carter, <i>et al.</i> , 2018 [200]	T2D, overweight / obese 60.5±9.2 36.0±5.8	12 months Parallel randomized clinical trial	97	Intermittent energy restriction group (IER) Continuous energy restriction group (CER)	IER: 500-600kcal/day for 2 non-consecutive days of the week, usual diet for the other 5 days CER: 1200-1500kcal/day Similar weekly energy restrictions	BW -5kg in CER -6.8kg in IER HbA1c -0.5% in CER -0.2% in IER Ins -0.3% in CER -1.2% in IER
Carter, <i>et al.</i> , 2019 [201]	T2D, overweight / obese 62±9 35±4.8	12 months – 24-month follow-up Parallel randomized clinical trial	84	Intermittent energy restriction group (IER) Continuous energy restriction group (CER)	IER: 500-600kcal/day for 2 non-consecutive days of the week, usual diet for the other 5 days CER: 1200-1500kcal/day 24 months Follow-up	At 24 mo.: BW -3.9kg in CER -3.9kg in IER HbA1c +0.4% in CER +0.1% in IER TG

						-0.2±0.3 mmol/L in CER -0.02±0.2 mmol/L in IER
Varady, <i>et al.</i> , 2013 [202]	Normal BW/overweight) 47.5±2.5 2±1	12 weeks Randomized, controlled, parallel-arm feeding trial	30	ADF Control (ctrl)	ADF: 25% of E needs on fast day (~400-600kcal at 12:00h-14:00h), and <i>ad libitum</i> eating on each alternating feed day <i>ad libitum</i> eating every day	↓ BW in ADF -13% total Chol in ADF -20% TG in ADF -5% BP (systolic) in ADF -50% CRP in ADF
Catenacci, <i>et al.</i> , 2016 [203]	Obese 41.15±8.7 37.65±4.85	8-week intervention & 24 weeks unsupervised follow-up Randomized trial	26	CR (caloric restriction) ADF (alternate day fasting)	CR: -400kcal/day less than E needs ADF: <i>ad libitum</i> food in fed days, only water, calorie-free beverages and bouillon/stock cube soup on fast (0 kcal) days E distribution in both groups: 20% B, 30% L, 40% D and 10% snack	BW -7.1kg in CR at week 8 -8.2kg in ADF at week 8 -5kg in CR at week 12 -5.7kg in ADF at week 12 Glu (mg/dL) +3.3 in CR at week 8 +6 in ADF at week 8 +1.7 in CR at week 12 +2.6 in ADF at week 12 Ins (μU/mL) -0.2 in CR at week 8 +3 in ADF at week 8 -2 in CR at week 12

						+0.4 in ADF at week 12 TG (mg/dL) -2.8 in CR at week 8 -25 in ADF at week 8 +12 in CR at week 12 +5.1 in ADF at week 12
Trepanowski, <i>et al.</i> , 2017 [204]	Obese 44±11 34±4	12 months (6 mo. weight loss & 6 mo. maintenance)) RCT	69	Alternate day fasting group (ADF) Daily calorie restriction group (DCR) Control – No intervention group (ctrl)	ADF: 25% of energy needs on fast days; 125% of energy needs on alternating “feast days” DCR: calorie restriction to 75% of energy needs every day Ctrl: no-intervention control	<u>ADF vs ctrl:</u> At 6 months -6.8% BW -6.3 mg/dL Glu -7.5 µIU/mL Ins -2.49 HOMA-IR At 12 months -6% BW -3.9 mg/dL Glu -5.9 µIU/mL Ins -1.86 HOMA-IR <u>DCR vs ctrl:</u> At 6 months -6.8% BW -4.9 mg/dL Glu -7.0 µIU/mL Ins -2.56 HOMA-IR At 12 months -5.3% BW -9.6 mg/dL Glu -4.6 µIU/mL Ins -1.88 HOMA-IR

Gabel, <i>et al.</i> , 2019 [205]	Insulin resistant subjects 42±3 y.o. 35±1	12 months (6 mo. weight loss & 6 mo. maintenance) RCT	100 (43 complete)	Alternate-day fasting group (ADF) Daily calorie Restriction group (CR) Control group (ctrl)	6-months reduced net E intake by 25% Fasting days: 25% of E needs at lunch (12:00h-14:00h) Alternating feast days: 125% of E needs over 3 meals/day 6-mo. reduced net E intake by 25% per day over 3 meals every day 6-mo. weight maintenance phase: Both for ADF & CR groups → ADF consumed 50% of E needs on fast days and 150% on feast days → CR consumed 100% of E needs/day Instructed to maintain body weight	↓ weight (~18% for ADF, and ~14% for CR) Glu (mg/dL): no significant changes Ins (μIU/mL): -44% ADF 6 mo, -52% ADF 12 mo, -23% CR 6 mo, -14% CR 12 mo HOMA-IR: -48% ADF 6 mo, -54% ADF 12 mo, -19% CR 6 mo, -17% CR 12 mo
Hoddy, <i>et al.</i> , 2014 [206]	Obese 45.5±2.5 34.5±1	8 weeks Randomized, parallel-arm feeding trial	59	ADF-L Alternate day fasting – intake at lunch ADF-D Alternate day fasting – intake at dinner ADF-SM Alternate day fasting – intake in small meals	25% of E needs on fast day and <i>ad libitum</i> eating on feed day ADF-L: One meal (L) at 12.00h -14.00h on each fast day ADF-D: One meal (D) at 18.00h - 20.00h on each fast day ADF-SM: divided their fast day meal in 3 mini meals → 100 kcal at 6:00h -8:00, 300 kcal at 12:00h -14:00h and 100 kcal at 18:00h -20:00 on each fast day	BW -3.5kg in ADF-L -4.1kg in ADF-D -4.0kg in ADF-SM Glu -2% in ADF-L -1% in ADF-D -1% in ADF-SM Ins no change in ADF-L -18% in ADF-D -12% in ADF-SM HOMA-IR -10% in ADF-L

						<p>-27% in ADF-D -19% in ADF-SM</p> <p>TG -6% in ADF-L -8% in ADF-D -1% in ADF-SM</p>
Harvie, <i>et al.</i> , 2011 [214]	Overweight or obese 40±4 30.6±5.1	6 months Randomized trial	89	<p>Continuous energy restriction group (CER)</p> <p>Intermittent energy restriction group (IER)</p>	<p>CER: 25% restriction below estimated requirements for 7 days per week</p> <p>IER: 75% restriction for 2 days per week, with no restriction on the other 5 days per week</p> <p>25% PRO, 45% low GL CHO, 30% FAT (15% MUFAs, 7% SFAs, 7% PUFAs)</p>	<p>BW -5% in CER -7% in IER</p> <p>Ins -15% in CER -29% in IER</p> <p>HOMA -19% in CER -27% in IER</p> <p>Glu -2% in CER -2% in IER</p> <p>Adiponectin no change in CER +10% in IER</p> <p>Ghrelin +11% in CER +13% in IER</p> <p>TG -23% in CER -17% in IER</p>

						BP (systolic) -6% in CER -3% in IER
Harvie, <i>et al.</i> , 2013 [215]	Overweight 47.4±7.7 30.9±5.1	4 months (3 months weight loss and 1 month maintenance) Parallel randomized clinical trial	115	IECR: energy and CHO restriction IECR+PF: allowed <i>ad libitum</i> PRO and FAT DER: daily energy restriction	IECR: 25% overall E restriction, And for 2d/week restricted CHO (<40 g/d), On restricted days: 20% CHO, 45% PRO and 35% FAT IECR+PF: 25% overall E restriction, And for 2d/week restricted CHO (<40 g/d) and <i>ad libitum</i> PRO and FAT (MUFA and PUFA), On restricted days: 15% CHO, 35% PRO and 50% FAT DER: 25% overall E restriction, 45–50% CHO, 20–25% PRO and 30% FAT	BP (systolic) -6% in CER -3% in IER BW -5.5 kg in IECR -5.1 kg in IECR+PF -3.8 kg in DER Ins -21% in IECR -11% in IECR+PF -10% in DER HOMA-IR -25% in IECR -16% in IECR+PF -11% in DER HbA1c no change in HbA1c in all groups Glu no change in Glu in all groups TG -9% in IECR -14% in IECR+PF -7% in DER BP (systolic) -3% in IECR -13% in IECR+PF -9% in DER

• Time restricted Feeding (TRF)

<p>Hutchison, <i>et al.</i>, 2019 [193]</p>	<p>Overweight /Obese 55±3 33.9±0.8</p>	<p>14 exp. days Randomized crossover trial</p>	<p>15</p>	<p>TRFe TRFd</p>	<p>2 x 7 days separated by a 2-week washout</p> <p>Eating window: 8:00h-17:00h</p> <p>Eating window: 12:00h-21:00h</p> <p><i>Ad libidum water</i> and very low-calorie (<4 kcal/serving) drinks and foods</p>	<p>↓ BW on day 7</p> <p>iAUC_{Glu} -36% in TRFe -21% in TRFd</p> <p>No effect on fasting Glu, Ins, (but a ↓ trend)</p> <p>↓ mean fasting Glu for TRFe vs baseline</p> <p>↓ 3hr ppd Glu for TRFe vs baseline</p>
<p>Wehrens, <i>et al.</i>, 2017 [194]</p>	<p>Normal BW/Overweight 18-30 20-30</p>	<p>13 exp. Days Human laboratory trial</p>	<p>10</p>	<p>One group</p>	<p>Sleeping schedule: ~ 23:00-6:30h</p> <p>Day 1-3: Wake up at 6:30h, B at 7:00h, L at 12:00h, D at 17:00h</p> <p>Day 4-5: No treatment, measurements</p> <p>Day 6-11: Wake up at 6:30h, B at 12:00h, L at 17:00h, D at 22:00h</p> <p>Day 12-13: No treatment, measurements</p> <p>Isocaloric meals:</p>	<p>Late meals resulted in:</p> <p>↑ 5.69hr Glu acrophase (into sleeping time)</p> <p>↑ 1.5hr Ins acrophase</p> <p>↑ 1hr TG acrophase</p>

					55% CHO, 15% PRO, 30% FAT	
Jamshed, <i>et al.</i> , 2019 [195]	Overweight 32±7 30.1±2.7	8 days Randomized controlled crossover study	11	eTRF Control (ctrl)	6h feeding / 18h fasting Feeding: 8:00h to 14:00h B at 8:00h, L at 11:00h, and D at 14:00h 12h feeding / 12h fasting Feeding: 8:00h to 20:00h B at 8:00h, L at 14:00h, and D at 20:00h 3 daily meals were matched: 15% PRO, 50% CHO, 35% FAT 4 days in each condition – 3.5-5 weeks washout – 4 days in other condition	No significant changes in day Glu -7±2mg/dL night/sleep Glu in eTRF -4±1mg/dL 24-h blood Glu in eTRF -12±3mg/dL MAGE in eTRF -2±1mg/dL morning fasting Glu in eTRF -2.9±0.4mU/L morning fasting Ins in eTRF -0.73±0.11 HOMA-IR in eTRF +25±9% <i>IRS2</i> gene expression in eTRF +4.5±1.6mU/L evening fasting Ins in eTRF +1.09±0.43 evening HOMA-IR in eTRF No changes in <i>GLUT1</i> , <i>GLUT4</i> , or <i>IRS1</i> gene

						expression at either time of day
Wilkinson, <i>et al.</i> , 2020 [196]	Metabolic syndrome patients 59±11.14 33.06±4.76	12 weeks Single-arm, paired-sample trial	19	TRF	10h feeding / 14h nightly fasting Eating at will, subjects reported foods consumed via smartphone app (food and time logs)	<u>TRF vs baseline:</u> -3% BW -5% Blood Glu (CGM) -5% Fasting blood Glu -2% HbA1c -21% Fasting Ins -30% HOMA-IR
Sutton, <i>et al.</i> , 2018 [197]	Overweight with IGT 56±9 32.2±4.4	5 weeks Randomized, crossover trial (controlled feeding)	8	eTRF Control (ctrl)	eTRF: 6 hr eating window/day, 3 meals, dinner before 15:00h, ~18h fasting Ctrl: 12 hr eating period/day, 3 meals, ~12h fasting between 20:00h-6:30h Each plan for 5 weeks, with a 7-week washout period Isocaloric and eucaloric controlled feeding diets (BW maintenance) 15% PRO, 50% CHO, and 35% FAT	No weight loss Fasting Glu no significant changes Mean Glu no significant changes Fasting Ins -3.4±1.6 mU/L Mean Ins -26±9 mU/L Peak Ins -35±13 mU/L Insulinogenic index +14±7 mu/mg IR (iAUC) -36±10 mU/mg

Parr, <i>et al.</i> , 2020 [198]	T2D 50±8.9 34±4.8	6 weeks Pre-post non- randomized	19	Habitual diet (2 weeks) TRF (2 weeks)	Habitual diet: ~8400 kJ/d; 35% CHO, 20% PRO, 41% FAT, 1% alcohol 9h feeding / 15h fasting TRE diet: ~8500 kJ/d; 35% CHO, 19% PRO, 42% FAT, 1% alcohol Eating at will	No weight loss -3% HbA1c -3.6% Glu +18% Ins
Moro, <i>et al.</i> , 2016 [199]	Healthy athletes 29.21±3.8 BW 84.6±6.2Kg	8 weeks Randomized, single blind trial	34	TRF Normal Diet group (ND)	8h feeding / 16h fasting Meals: 13:00h (40% of total cal), 16:00h (25% of total cal), 20:00h (35% of total cal) Meals: 8:00h (25% of total cal), 13:00h (40% of total cal), 20:00h (35% of total cal)	↓ in fat mass -16.4% in TRF -2.8% in ND Glu -11% in TRF no change in ND Ins -36.3% in TRF -13% in ND

Abbreviations: B:Breakfast; L: Lunch; D: Dinner; E: energy; ppd: postprandial, Abbreviations: T2D: type 2 diabetes; IGT: impaired glucose tolerance; B:Breakfast; L: Lunch; D: Dinner; E: energy; ppd: postprandial, GI: Glycemic Index; GL: Glycemic Load; Glu: Glucose; Ins: Insulin; AUC: Area Under the Curve; iAUC: incremental area under the curve; CHO: carbohydrates; PRO: proteins; FAT: fats; TRF: time-restricted feeding; CGM: continuous glucose monitoring; BW: body weight; RCT: randomized controlled clinical trial; HOMA: homeostatic model assessment for insulin; TG: triglycerides; BP: blood pressure